

Characterization of the Phenolate-Keto Oxyluciferin/Luciferase Interactions in the S_1 State by QM/MM Energy Decomposition Analysis

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Abstract

Unraveling the nature of the interaction on the complex formed by the oxyluciferin chromophore in the first electronically excited state and the luciferase enzyme can lead to a more profound understanding of fireflies' bioluminescence, which is a natural process with a large amount of applications in medicine. In this work, we have studied the interaction of the phenolate-keto OLU chromophore and the luciferase protein, and we have found that the interaction energy is governed mostly by electrostatic terms.

Nonetheless, non-electrostatic contributions are non-negligible due to the high presence of π -system-containing amino acids within the bioluminescent pocket. Furthermore, we have outlined a methodology for performing energy decomposition analysis in the excited state using a multiscale hybrid electrostatic-embedding QM/MM approach, stressing that the OLUFF force field is not suitable for this task from a force field-base approach. Moreover, we have analyzed how the proximity of PHE249 and SER349 affect the different terms of the interaction energy, unraveling that the most relevant terms of their contributions are polarization and electrostatic, respectively. This strategy can be extended to investigate the interactions of the other three potential emitters within the OLU/luciferase complex, as well as complexes with mutated proteins. Such analyses may help clarify the factors governing colour modulation in the bioluminescent process and provide valuable insights for tuning the OLU/luciferase complex to enhance its applicability.

Introduction

The oxyluciferin (OLU)/luciferase complex is the natural biochemical system where fireflies' bioluminescence is originated.¹⁻⁹ This process consists on a two-step reaction in which D-luciferin is first adenylated by adenosine triphosphate (ATP) via a SN_2 nucleophilic displacement and then oxidized by an oxygen molecule. As a result from this luciferase-catalyzed reaction, OLU in the first electronically excited state (S_1) is produced, from which the characteristic fireflies' green light is emitted upon radiative relaxation. Even though the biochemical reaction leading to the formation of the emitting specie was extensively studied, it is still unclear which of the six possible tautomers of the OLU chromophore is the one responsible for the light emission.¹⁰ Nonetheless, two of them, namely, phenol-enol and phenolate-enol, were completely discarded since they undergo a very fast excited state proton transfer to its monoanionic forms which, at the same time, present a very fast relaxation to the OLU phenolate-enolate form. This work exclusively focuses on the phenolate-keto OLU,

represented in Figure 1(A), to fully characterize the chromophore/protein interactions in the S_1 state since it is the direct product of the bioluminescence reaction and has been found to be one of the emitting species.

The study of fireflies' bioluminescent system is currently under an extensive research because it presents a large number of applications in medicine. For example, it can be used to detect ATP in extracellular and intracellular media, thus allowing to monitor mitochondrial functioning¹¹ and to detect contamination of sterilized environments^{12,13} and carcinogenic cells.¹⁴⁻¹⁷ Furthermore, it can be used as light source in bioimaging employed for cell tracking, the study of neuro degenerative diseases,¹⁸⁻²³ and the analysis of reporter genes^{24,25} and protein-protein interactions.²⁶⁻³⁰ In order to improve the performance of the system by, for example, being able to control colour of the emitted light, and to extend its already large number of applications, it is important to fully understand its nature. In previous works, we discussed the structural behavior of the phenolate-keto OLU chromophore inside the luciferase pocket.³¹ However, to achieve a better understanding of the emission process, it is quite relevant to characterize the nature of the ligand/protein interactions as detailed binding affinities have not been determined yet for all OLU analogues.¹⁰ Thus, in this work the interaction energy between the OLU chromophore and the luciferase protein is calculated by means of the force field terms and Time-Dependent Density Functional Theory (TD-DFT) and then, the different interaction energy contributions are analyzed using one-Average Molecular-Mechanics Generalized Born Surface-Area (1A-MM-GBSA) and Quantum Mechanics/Molecular Mechanics Energy Decomposition Analysis (QM/MM-EDA), respectively. The QM/MM-EDA protocol provides much more accurate results than a simple energy analysis based on force field contributions, as discussed along this work. Furthermore, this work provides a computational protocol for the calculation and analysis of the interaction energy for systems in electronically excited states that may be applied to the three remaining plausible OLU emitters as well as other chromophores interacting with complex environments.

Figure 1: (A) Oxyluciferin/luciferase complex with the 15 amino acids with the largest pairwise total binding free energy in pink. (B) Pairwise residue decomposition based on the 1A-MM-GBSA approach of the total binding free energy (ΔG^{tot}) and the van der Waals (ΔG^{vdW}), electrostatic (ΔG^{elec}), polar solvation (ΔG^{pol}), non-polar (ΔG^{np}) solvation terms including the 40 residues that are located at shortest distances from OLU along the simulation. At the bottom of the plot, between parenthesis, the total binding Gibbs free energy of the chromophore is shown and, at the right-hand side, the binding Gibbs free energy per residue are shown for the 15 amino acids with the largest contributions.

Computational Details

This study was carried out for the phenolate-keto OLU emitter in the first electronically excited state within the luciferase environment. The chromophore/enzyme system was built from the X-ray diffraction structure file of the Japanese firefly luciferase (PDB ID: 2D1R).³² In order to obtain a thermally averaged ensemble of geometries for the analysis of the interaction energy with both 1A-MM-GBSA and QM/MM-EDA approaches, a 1.4 μs classical molecular dynamics (MD) simulation was performed based on potential gradients computed

by the recently published OLU force field (OLUFF) for the chromophore,³³ a reparameterized version of the General Amber force field (GAFF)³⁴ for the adenosine monophosphate (AMP), the ff19SB46³⁵ force field for the protein and the TIP3P³⁶ model for the Na⁺ cations and water molecules. A full description of the computational protocol followed for the classical dynamics can be found in our previous work.³¹

To study the nature of the total interaction energy in the S₁ state, the aforementioned ensemble of geometries was employed. In a first stage, the binding free energy was calculated by means of the 1A-MM-GBSA approach^{37,38} using the *MMPBSA.py* tool.³⁹ Moreover, this binding free energy was decomposed into amino acid contributions to determine those amino acids presenting a higher contribution to the interaction energy, as shown in Figure 1(B). Next, the QM/MM-EDA analysis was performed using a scheme based on electron deformation densities.⁴⁰⁻⁴² In order to ensure meaningful results, a minor benchmarking of the DFT/basis set combination was performed and the convergence of the different interaction energy terms with respect to (i) the number of amino acids in the QM region of the protein and (ii) the number of sampled geometries was evaluated. As conclusion of these analysis, it was found that optimal results are obtained at the M062X⁴³/6-31G(2d,p)⁴⁴⁻⁴⁸ level of theory including 15 amino acids in the QM region of the protein, and that at least 125 geometries are necessary to get converged average values for all the interaction energy terms. Specific details on these calculations can be found in Sections 1-3 of the SI.

Results and discussion

As previously mentioned, understanding the OLU/luciferase interaction in the excited state is crucial for modulating the photochemical properties of the system. From a classical perspective, the interaction energy can be calculated from the different terms of the force field by means of the 1A-MM-GBSA approach,^{37,38} which further allows the pairwise per residue characterization of the different energetic terms, namely: van der Waals, electrostatic, polar

solvation and non-polar solvation terms. Within this classical framework, most of the binding free energy comes from the van der Waals contribution, as shown in Table 1. This means that the stabilization of the OLU inside the active pocket would come from dispersion and inductive forces, while the electrostatic term would not play a significant role in the stabilization. Moreover, as observed in Figure 1(B), the 15 amino acids with the largest total binding free energy, in decreasing order of interaction, are PHE249, SER349, ALA350, GLY343, HIE247, GLY318, GLY341, GLY248, GLY317, THR253, TYR342, LEU344, ILE353, THR345 and PHE252. Among them, only PHE249 and SER349 present a binding free energy below -4 kcal/mol, which are dominated by van der Waals and electrostatic terms, respectively. Furthermore, there are two amino acids that present strong electrostatic stabilization (ALA220 and ARG339), and another with significant polar solvation (GLU346). However, this stabilization is offset by either the polar solvation or electrostatic terms, leading to a very small contribution to the total binding free energy of the OLU/luciferase complex.

In order to obtain a more accurate description of the intermolecular interactions responsible for the stability of the OLU/luciferase complex, the interaction energy and its different components were obtained at QM/MM level. In the original QM-EDA scheme employed in this study, the total interaction energy is divided into three different terms: the electrostatic energy, accounting for the presence of effective charges and multipole moments; the Pauli repulsion energy, arising from the Pauli exclusion principle and further divided into attractive (intermolecular exchange) and repulsive (repulsion) terms; and the polarization energy, which depends on the polarization density and can be approximated as summation of induction and dispersion energies using a second-order perturbation expansion of the polarization density.

In the case of biological systems, and due to computational constraints, accurate and meaningful results of the substrate/protein interactions at QM level can only be achieved by means of a QM/MM framework. Herein, the QM region of the calculation includes a representative amount of the biomolecule, in this particular case the amino acids of the

active site, while the rest of the biomolecule is replaced by a MM electrostatic embedding. In practice, point charges of the MM region are added to the Hamiltonian during the QM calculation of the complex and fragments as well as to the subsequent calculations of the different interaction energy terms.

Nonetheless, the selection of the amino acids that should be included in the QM region is not trivial. Furthermore, biological systems also require a large sampling from the MD simulation so that converged results are obtained in the energy analysis. In this work, we first studied the convergence of the QM/MM-EDA with respect to the number of amino acids in the QM region of the proteic monomer and then its convergence with the number of frames selected from MD simulation. Moreover, for selection of the amino acids of the QM region, the proposed workflow relies on the 1A-MM-GBSA approach to determine which amino acids, among the closest during the MD trajectory, present a greater contribution to the total interaction energy, as represented in Figure 1(B). However, since the main goal is to investigate the interactions in the S_1 state, this approach is not ideal because, even though the force field is parameterized to perform the sampling in the excited state, the only reliable non-bonding term of the OLUFF is the electrostatic one as Lennard–Jones parameters are taken from the General Amber FF,³⁴ which is parameterized for the ground state.

Initially, the twenty amino acids with the largest binding Gibbs free energy according to the 1A-MM-GBSA approach were included one by one in decreasing order of contribution in the QM region for the TD-DFT calculations and then the QM/MM-EDA was performed for the representative structure of the trajectory (see details in the SI). As it can be observed in Figure 2(A), Pauli, induction and dispersion are fully converged when fifteen amino acids, those stressed in Figure 1(B), were included in the QM region while the electrostatic contribution is still slightly decreasing. This is not surprising due to the fact that electrostatic energy presents a strong long-range character and thus is more difficult to converge. However, since the difference compared to a QM region of twenty amino acids is only 3.4%, we considered all the terms to be converged when fifteen amino acids are included in the QM

region.

Figure 2: (A) Convergence of the interaction energy and its different components with the number of amino acids in the QM region. (B) Number of transferred electrons between the two monomers (green) and averaged position of the orbital before and after the electronic transition (orange).

It is important to mention that the interaction energy calculation, and therefore the EDA decomposition, in electronically excited complexes is only reliable if the electronic excitation is located on just one monomer (in this case, the OLU chromophore). Otherwise, if the

excitation entails substantial charge transfer (CT) between monomers, an electronic excited state localized on a single monomer would fail to adequately represent the charge densities of the isolated monomers. In these cases, a weighted superposition of excitations on both monomers would provide a more appropriate description. To investigate this issue, the transition density matrix was analyzed to calculate the number of transferred electrons between the two monomers and the mean position of the orbital before and after the electronic transition (POS). POS values of 1 or 2 indicate that the electron is localized on monomer 1 or 2, respectively, both before and after the electronic transition, whereas a value of 1.5 indicates perfect delocalization between the two monomers. As it can be observed in Figure 2(B), the protein environment does not participate in the excited state because there is no CT character and the POS is localized in the OLU chromophore. Thus, the interaction energy calculation and the subsequent QM/MM-EDA can be easily performed using the OLU excited state and the protein ground state as references for the isolated monomer densities.

As mentioned before, not only the number of amino acids in the QM region has to be converged, it is also important to have a good conformational sampling of the system, i.e., a sufficiently large number of snapshots for the analysis of the properties. Thus, QM/MM-EDA calculations were performed on 1, 2, 5, 10, 25, 50, 125 and 250 equidistant geometries from the MD trajectory. This analysis was carried out on electronically excited complexes localized on a single monomer (see Figure S4). As it can be observed in Figure 3, all the interaction energy components are converged when 125 snapshots were considered in the analysis. Therefore, the 250 snapshots for which the energies were computed are more than enough to obtain reliable results.

Figure 3: (A-G) Convergence of the interaction energy and its different components with respect to the number of geometries.

Once convergence of the energetic terms is guaranteed, we can focus on the analysis and discussion of the results. First, the probability distributions of the total interaction energy and its components are shown in Figure 4. It can be observed that the different energy components are not distributed similarly as their distributions present different broadness. Furthermore, as previously demonstrated,⁴⁹ the broadness of the distribution is associated with the magnitude of the average value (see Table 1). These results show that the phenolate-keto OLU/luciferase interaction in the S_1 state is very favorable and that the electrostatic character is predominant over Pauli and polarization. These results are radically opposite to the results obtained with the 1A-MM-GBSA approach. Thus, the classical model strongly underestimates the electrostatic interaction (17.0% vs 90.4%) and overestimates the van der

Waals term (83.0% vs 9.6%). The van der Waals contribution corresponds to the sum of the Pauli and polarization terms in the QM/MM-EDA framework. This overestimation of the van der Waals contribution is likely a consequence of the underestimation of the Pauli repulsion by the force field, as previously observed.⁴⁹ A proper description of the Pauli repulsion would partially cancel out the attractive interactions and, as a result, the van der Waals energy would be less important at classical level. Therefore, while the 1A-MM-GBSA approach erroneously states that the interaction is mostly due to van der Waals forces, the QM/MM-EDA shows that the interaction is, in fact, of electrostatic character.

Figure 4: Energy distributions of the interaction energy and its different components calculated from the QM/MM-EDA on 250 geometries.

Table 1: Averages and standard deviations of the interaction energy and its different components obtained with the 1A-MM-GBSA and QM/MM-EDA methodologies on 250 geometries. Percentages are relative to the sum of electrostatic and van der Waals terms (1A-MM-GBSA) and electrostatic and pauli+polarization (EDA).

1A-MM-GBSA			EDA		
Contribution	Energy (kcal/mol)	%	Contribution	Energy (kcal/mol)	%
Electrostatic	-8.5 ± 8.3	17.0	Electrostatic	-112.9 ± 9.7	90.4
			Pauli	48.9 ± 8.8	-
van der Waals	-41.4 ± 2.0	83.0	Polarization	-60.9 ± 5.6	-
			van der Waals	-12.0 ± 4.9	9.6
Polar	19.2 ± 8.0	-	Dispersion	-47.1 ± 4.9	-
Non-polar	-3.86 ± 0.11	-	Induction	-13.8 ± 1.8	-
Total	-34.6 ± 3.5	-	Total	-124.8 ± 9.0	-

Finally, the effect of the proximity of PHE249 and SER349 amino acids was analyzed (Table 2). To do so, the 250 geometries selected for the QM/MM-EDA were divided according to the distance between the center of mass of the OLU chromophore and that of each amino acid in two sets of 100 frames, each with the shortest and the largest distances. The selection of these two amino acids was not arbitrary, as they are the two amino acids that interact more strongly with the OLU according to the 1A-MM-GBSA approach. Moreover, our previous work³¹ demonstrated a significant presence of PHE249 during the MD simulations, which may affect the attractive polarization component of the interaction energy. In fact, in the case of the PHE249, the total interaction energy of OLU with the environment is very similar regardless of the proximity of this amino acid (-124.8 ± 9.6 kcal/mol for a distance of 3.92 ± 0.09 Å and -124.7 ± 8.7 kcal/mol for a distance of 4.3 ± 0.1 Å) as a consequence of the decrease in the Pauli repulsion (7.1 kcal/mol), which offsets the decrease of the attractive electrostatic and polarization terms (7.2 kcal/mol). Furthermore, it can be observed that the decrease in the electrostatic energy is less pronounced (2.5 kcal/mol) than the decrease in the polarization term (4.7 kcal/mol) when this amino acid is farther. Hence, it can be concluded that OLU-PHE249 interactions present a large polarization contribution, which is consistent with the nature of the system, where the stacking interactions must be relevant.

On the flip side, the presence of SER349 in the vicinity of the phenolate-keto OLU ($4.98 \pm 0.08 \text{ \AA}$) certainly contributes to the complex stabilization as a decrease of 3.0 kcal/mol , in absolute value, in the total interaction energy is observed when this amino acid is farther ($5.3 \pm 0.1 \text{ \AA}$) from the chromophore. This decrease in the interaction energy is mostly due to a decrease in the electrostatic contribution (5.7 kcal/mol in absolute value), which is larger than that of the polarization term (2.4 kcal/mol in absolute value). In this case, the decrease of the Pauli repulsion (5.2 kcal/mol) is not able to fully counteract the most favorable attractive interactions. In contrast to PHE249, when SER349 moves farther from the OLU, the electrostatic contribution decreases more than the polarization term. Thus, it can be concluded that the OLU-SER349 interactions present an electrostatic nature, which is consistent to the presence of the alcohol group in its lateral chain.

Table 2: Averages and standard deviations of the EDA components calculated from 100 frames out of the 250 EDA calculations in which the amino acids PHE249 and SER349 were closest or farthest to OLU. Energies are in kcal/mol.

Contribution	PHE249		SER349	
	Closest	Farthest	Closest	Farthest
Electrostatic	-114.2 ± 10.2	-111.7 ± 9.5	-116.0 ± 9.9	-110.3 ± 9.1
Pauli	52.7 ± 8.3	45.6 ± 8.7	51.7 ± 8.9	46.5 ± 8.3
Polarization	-63.4 ± 5.2	-58.7 ± 5.3	-62.2 ± 5.7	-59.8 ± 5.6
Dispersion	-49.2 ± 4.6	-45.2 ± 4.4	48.0 ± 5.1	-46.0 ± 4.7
Induction	-14.1 ± 1.7	-13.5 ± 1.9	-14.2 ± 1.9	-13.7 ± 1.6
Total	-124.8 ± 9.6	-124.7 ± 8.7	-126.4 ± 8.7	-123.4 ± 8.8

Conclusions

In this work, we applied a methodology to perform EDA on electronically excited states by means of a multiscale hybrid electrostatic-embedding QM/MM approach. Specifically, this methodology was employed to study the interaction of the phenolate-keto OLU in the first electronically excited state and the luciferase protein, which is the system responsible of fireflies' bioluminescence. We have evidenced: (i) the clear need of a QM treatment for the calculation of interaction energies as the OLUFF fails to reproduce the importance of

the different energy terms (ii); the importance of considering a sufficiently large QM region (15 amino acids of the protein plus the OLU chromophore); and (iii) the relevance of a good conformational sampling since wide energy distributions are obtained.

Quantum mechanical calculations and QM/MM-EDA analysis revealed that the interaction of the OLU with the luciferase protein in the electronically excited state is mostly governed by the electrostatic term, although non-electrostatic contributions are not negligible due to the presence of amino acids with π systems inside the active site of the protein, PHE249 being the most important. In addition, the relevance of the SER349 residue was highlighted, which mainly interacts electrostatically with the chromophore.

The methodology presented here can be applied to explore not only the interaction between the other three possible emitters of the OLU/luciferase complex, but also additional complexes with mutated proteins. This would help to elucidate the factors that affect the color modulation of the bioluminescent process. Moreover, different complexes with excited chromophores could also be analyzed.

Data Availability

Both *Pymol*⁵⁰ (<https://pymol.org/>) and the *tleap* toolkit from the AmberTools22⁵¹ package were used to generate the topology and coordinate files for the MD simulations. The *PMEMD.CUDA* module⁵²⁻⁵⁴ of the AMBER22 (<https://ambermd.org/>) software was used to perform the classical MD simulations. Afterwards, the *cpptraj* toolkit⁵⁵ from the AmberTools22 package was used to analyze the geometric features of the MD simulations and the *MMPBSA.py* tool³⁹ was used to calculate the 1A-MM-GBSA. As for the QM/MM and EDA calculations, the necessary inputs for the software Gaussian09⁵⁶ were automatically prepared by means of the MoBioTools toolkit⁵⁷ (<https://github.com/mobiochem/MoBioTools>), the EDA were calculated using the EDA-NCI program (<https://github.com/marcos-mandado/EDA-NCI>) and the one-electron transition density matrix was analyzed by means of the TheoDORE

software.⁵⁸ Finally, homemade scripts were generated with Python 3 (<https://www.python.org/>) in order to perform the data analysis of the results. All the necessary files to reproduce the QM/MM and EDA calculations can be found in the Zenodo repository DOI:10.5281/zenodo.17638020.

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Supporting Information Available

Supporting Information contains a discussion about the benchmark of functionals and basis sets, and the convergence with the number of amino acids. In addition, all the necessary input files for Gaussian, MMGBSA files, and all analysis data necessary to generate figures of this manuscript can be found in the Zenodo repository DOI:10.5281/zenodo.17638020. Moreover, the following files are available free of charge.

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